

No One-Size-Fits-All: Distinct Mental Health Pathways among Homemakers

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Summary

1. We examine how the mental health of homemakers—people staying at home while their partner works—compares to when they were working, using Dutch population register data (2006–2021).
2. Female homemakers without minor children use primary mental health care less after leaving work, suggesting improved mental health.
3. Male homemakers and women with minor children maintain similar mental health to when they were working.
4. Homemaking itself does not affect antidepressant prescriptions; however, prescriptions appear to increase for some women prior to transitioning from work to homemaking.
5. The mental health influence of homemaking is unaffected by its duration.
6. Policies should recognize homemakers as a distinct group from other economically inactive individuals and address diverse needs within the group.

1. Introduction

Homemakers—those staying at home while their partner works—often report higher happiness and life satisfaction than workers (Hamplová, 2019; Treas et al., 2011). Yet little is known about their mental health, which has a more complex relationship with happiness

and life satisfaction than it may seem (Agterén & Iasiello, 2020). For instance, individuals may report high levels of happiness during a manic phase while simultaneously experiencing an underlying depressive disorder. In this policy brief, we highlight the study we recently conducted (Kröner et al., 2025a) in which we investigate (1) how the mental health of homemakers compares to their mental health while they were working,

and (2) whether this differs by gender, parenthood, and homemaking duration.

The Dutch government highlights the historically tight labor market, just like many other European countries, and plans to boost labor participation by tapping into unused labor potential, among which also homemakers (Rijksoverheid, 2024).

In terms of (re)-employment, mental health has shown to be a key factor for other inactive individuals (Vinokur & Price, 2015), but has not been considered for homemakers.

Previous research has largely focused on homemakers' well-being but has often overlooked mental health problems and paid insufficient attention to heterogeneity. Research often centers on mothers (Hamplová, 2019; Kühn et al., 2023; Langner, 2022), overlooking other homemakers, such as women without minor children, who are well represented in the Netherlands (Kröner et al., 2025b), and also particularly men.

2. The context and the analysis

We use Dutch administrative register data covering the full population aged 18–45 between 2006 and 2021. This includes information on employment, demographics, mental health care service use, and antidepressant prescriptions. The data include 1,187,103 observations from 165,984 individuals who were in a partnership and transitioned from work to homemaking between 2006 and 2021.

We assess mental health through primary mental health care service use (e.g., counseling, cognitive behavioral therapy) and antidepressant prescriptions (ATC No6A). The Dutch context—where almost the entire population is covered by statutory health

insurance and thus included in (medical) register data—allows us to shift the focus from homemakers' subjective well-being to their mental health in terms of mental health conditions.

We use fixed-effects individual slopes (FEIS) models with dummy impact functions (Ludwig & Brüderl, 2021; Prechsl & Wolbring, 2023). Compared to commonly used fixed-effects models, FEIS accounts for individual-specific linear trends over time, ensuring that the observed effects are not driven by pre-existing up- or downward trends in antidepressant prescriptions or primary mental health care use, but rather reflect changes directly associated with homemaking.

3. Results

We report three key findings. First, female homemakers without minor children show better mental health. After accounting for all observed and unobserved heterogeneity at the individual level, these women used fewer primary mental health services after becoming homemakers. No similar pattern was found for male homemakers or for mothers of minor children, whose use of primary mental health services does not differ significantly between working and homemaking.

Second, for women without minor children, antidepressant prescriptions rise about 10% before homemaking and remain elevated. Prescriptions already begin to increase by roughly 5% in the year before leaving paid work. Given the relatively small overlap between those who use primary mental health care services and those who are prescribed antidepressants, our findings indicate distinct groups of homemakers in terms of mental health and the treatment they seek. This

suggests that, for some women, mental health problems may contribute to the decision to become a homemaker, while for others, mental health improves as reflected in declining use of primary mental health services after transitioning from paid work to homemaking.

Third, the mental health influence of homemaking is unaffected by the duration of homemaking. Contrary to consistent evidence from unemployment research showing that mental health declines the longer individuals remain outside the labor market (Paul & Moser, 2009), mental health does not deteriorate over longer periods of homemaking.

4. Policy recommendations

Our findings have important implications for society and policy on health and the labor market.

First, **recognize homemakers as a distinct group in policy debates.** The share of women without their own income, mostly homemakers, has declined from 10 to 6 percent over the past decade. Nevertheless, with 313,000 women in 2024 (CBS, 2025; Kröner et al. 2025c), they remain, as probably in other countries with high female labor force participation a relevant group, which appears to differ in mental health from other economically inactive individuals, such as the unemployed.

Second, **differentiate (re)employment strategies.** Mental health should primarily be considered for women without minor children when designing re-employment strategies from homemaking to work. But even within this group a closer monitoring would be necessary. For men and women with minor children, there appears to be no

significant difference in mental health between homemaking and working, suggesting that other strategies may be more effective.

Third, **implement targeted mental health interventions.** Among female homemakers without minor children, some show rising antidepressant use prior to leaving paid work, which remains elevated afterward. For others, a decline in primary mental health service use during homemaking may mask concerns about a potential relapse when returning to work. Supporting mental health in this group could therefore facilitate their (re)integration into employment, similar to strategies aimed at breaking the “vicious cycle” of unemployment and mental health problems (Trimbos Institute, 2020).

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Further Information:

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